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Research Article

**AWARENESS AND KNOWLEDGE OF NURSING CARE IN
EAR, NOSE AND THROAT DISORDERS**Dr Khadija Mariyum¹, Dr Muhammad Adeel ur Rahim², Dr Abdul Rahman³¹Rawalpindi Medical University²Medical Officer, RHC Ahmed Pur Lamma, Sadiqabad, Rahim Yar Khan.**Article Received:** September 2020 **Accepted:** October 2020 **Published:** November 2020**Abstract:**

Background and objectives: Diseases of the ear, nose and throat (ENT) are universally a significant general health concern. The Global Burden of Disease (GBD), including ENT conditions, has consistently been accounted for to be relative to asset deprivation. This study aimed to analyse the nursing care in ear, nose and throat disorders. **Methodology of the study:** This prospective cross-sectional study was done in RMC during January 2019 to July 2019. The data was collected through a questionnaire. The data was collected from those patients who visited the hospital for ENT disorders. The data collection team consist of ENT specialists, audiologists and hospital nurses. The hospital was well equipped with an operating microscope and ENT instruments. **Results:** The data was collected from 100 patients which were appropriate for our inclusion criteria. We observe all the symptoms that were commonly present in patients. So that we can identify the care related to these symptoms and problems of ENT. According to our results the group B which were handled with trained nurses for ENT nursing care were showed the better results as compared to group A who have less knowledge of nursing care. **Conclusion:** It is concluded that creating awareness of the common ENT conditions and how they are caused and treatment options available help decrease the burden of the disease in the community.

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INTRODUCTION:

Diseases of the ear, nose and throat (ENT) are universally a significant general health concern. The Global Burden of Disease (GBD), including ENT conditions, has consistently been accounted for to be relative to asset deprivation. Despite the fact that created nations are not exclude from the high ENT malady trouble, low pay African and Asian nations are generally influenced [1]. All around, incapacitating hearing misfortune influences around 466 million individuals, weakening individual sufferers, families and nations the same. Head and neck cancer, the ninth most normal harm, has high death rates in creating nations. In most of spots, people with correspondence troubles are not organized in health care frameworks as governments center around sparing lives rather than improving personal satisfaction [2].

Numerous patients with states of the ear, nose, and throat report a scope of various side effects and expectation their internist can recommend a cure that will lighten their wretchedness and cause them to feel better rapidly [3]. The most widely recognized ENT states of sinusitis, hearing misfortune, vertigo, and tinnitus can be assessed and treated in the essential care office, however indications of an intense or extreme condition should provoke a referral to a subspecialist, specialists concurred [4].

The most well-known issues justifying a visit to a specialist or a health care supplier in creating nations are related to ear nose and throat (ENT). ENT issues are the most widely recognized issues for which there are home solutions for medical treatments which are accessible, and most people deal with their concern in the network without looking for help [5]. What's more, because of the absence of authority experts right now, issues are treated by network rehearses. The investigations done have taken a gander at the commonness of ENT illnesses in kids and have indicated that the infection trouble is because of otitis media and its sequelae which are the most well-known reasons for preventable hearing misfortune in kids in creating nations [6].

The prevalence of traditional practices increased the disease morbidity requiring surgical management. Postal review utilizing survey techniques was utilized to evaluate the commonness of ENT-related issue in a network [7]. There is no data on the commonness of otorhinolaryngological illnesses in a rustic network in India. The present examination was embraced to decide the commonness of ENT issue in population presenting to an auxiliary care emergency clinic with

accentuation on essential care in country networks and innate territory [8].

A few issues of the ear, nose and throat (ENT) are normal; the vast majority sooner or later in their lives experience the ill effects of nosebleeds, sore throats or ear infection. A large number of these issues will be managed effectively at home, regularly with the exhortation of a drug specialist or general expert (GP) [9]. Some ENT issues, in any case, can be perilous, requiring a quick visit to a crisis department (ED), medical procedure and, sometimes, a time of nursing care at home after release [10].

To nurse ENT patients effectively in a home or emergency clinic setting, a fundamental information on the life structures and physiology of the applicable structures, alongside an exhaustive understanding of the clinical highlights of normal issue, is essential [11]. The health guest, network nurse, school nurse or word related health nurse is regularly in a situation to recognize issues before the medical specialist or even the patient knows about them [12].

This study aimed to analyse the nursing care in ear, nose and throat disorders.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY:

This prospective cross sectional study was done in RMC during January 2019 to July 2019.

Study design

We divided this study into two groups, Group A and Group B.

Group A: Patients were handled with non-trained staff and nurses for ENT care.

Group B: Patients were handled with trained staff and nurses for nursing care of ENT disorders.

Data collection

The data was collected through a questionnaire. The data was collected from those patients who visited the hospital for ENT disorders. The data collection team consist of ENT specialists, audiologists and hospital nurses. The hospital was well equipped with an operating microscope and ENT instruments. The hospital staff and nurses were taught about safe ear care practices, the harmful effects of prevalent traditional practices, and the treatment options available. They know how to identify the ENT disorders e.g. ear pain with or without discharge, sour throat, respiratory tract infection, throat pain, swelling, difficulty in eating and fever. The age range for this study was 10 to 50 years. Questionnaire method of data collection was used to know the prevalence of

ENT-related conditions and analysing the nursing care in ENT disorders. This questionnaire include all the questions related to nursing care of ENT disorders.

Statistical analysis

All data were displayed in mean $\pm$ SD and analysed through SPSS 19.0 (IBM, USA). T-test and one-way ANOVA were applied for measuring comparison among groups. $P < 0.05$ was considered to have statistical meaning.

RESULTS:

The data was collected from 100 patients which were appropriate for our inclusion criteria. We observe all

the symptoms that were commonly present in patients. So that we can identify the care related to these symptoms and problems of ENT. According to our results the group B which were handled with trained nurses for ENT nursing care were showed the better results as compared to group A who have less knowledge of nursing care. Subsequent to preparing, the mean score for the test in the gathering B expanded to 68%, demonstrating a measurably huge improvement from benchmark ($p < 0.001$). There was additionally upgrades in information for the individual modules, and appraisal and directing.

Table 1: Analysis of questionnaire of nursing care in ENT disorders

Module	Analysis of questionnaire		Significance
	Group A	Group B	
Structure and function of the ear	56%	61%	<0.0001
Hearing impairment and deafness: causes and prevention	51%	53%	<0.0001
The outer ear: examine, treat and refer	52%	63%	<0.0001
The ear canal: examine, diagnose and clean	51%	67%	0.03
The middle ear: examine, diagnose and treat	50%	58%	0.28
Assessing hearing and counselling	62%	79%	0.17
All modules	48%	65%	<0.0001

The majority of the nurses (77%) said that the length of the training was right, whereas 23% thought that it was too short. In dealing with patients with ENT disorders, 62% reported that they felt comfortable and 38% felt very comfortable after the training. None of the nurses reported feeling uncomfortable in this study. According to our results 60% of the patients showed pain and discharge in throat disorders, 29% ear and 11% nose disorders.

DISCUSSION:

There is need to accomplish more research on the arrangement of demonstrative and helpful PEHC benefits by CHWs and general health workers at bleeding edge health offices. With the approach of a lot of programming applications for audiometry, there is need to look at the feasibility of outfitting the CHWs with the gadget [13]. Moreover, research is needed concerning which helpful methodologies are proper at the essential level. For example, essential healthcare laborers are frequently educated to do dry cleaning for wet holes. Among our patients with wet holes, various them had dead house flies in the ears which may have been hard to expel with dry wiping alone [14]. Proof is additionally needed regarding whether ear syringing might be valuable for these kind of conditions [15].

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that creating awareness of the common ENT conditions and how they are caused and treatment options available help decrease the burden of the disease in the community. Utilizing prepared nursing care staff to spread the message of safe ENT rehearses, gives restoration of hearing misfortune through arrangement of hearing guides, and the assessment and careful administration by the pro (when seven days) helped the provincial network to get to the administration.

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